

3D additive manufactured 316L components microstructural features and changes induced by working life cycles

M.L. Pace (1), A. Guarnaccio (1), P. Dolce (1), D. Mollica (1), G.P. Parisi (1), A. Lettino (2), L. Medici (2), V. Summa (2), R. Ciancio (3), A. Santagata (1)

(1)CNR – ISM, MATFUN Tito Scalo Unit, Zona Industriale, 85050 Tito Scalo (PZ) - ITALY

(2)CNR – IMAA, Zona Industriale, 85050 Tito Scalo (PZ) - ITALY

(3)CNR-IOM TASC, Area Science Park Basovizza, 34136 Trieste (TS) – ITALY

Abstract

The ability of processing through laser beams different kinds of metallic powders for direct production of 3D components with complex geometries has been gaining an impressive and growing attention for specific industrial applications. The process which can be distinguished as Selective Laser Sintering or Selective Laser Melting is even considered, more generally, as Additive Manufacturing where layer by layer material is built by the interaction between a laser beam and a powder bed. The rapid heating of the powder due to the laser beam energy transfer process followed by a rapid cooling rate induces within the manufactured material a cellular structure with fine sub-grains, which are in the range of few hundreds of micrometers. These metastable structures, which are smaller than the grain size in conventionally manufactured 316L stainless steel components, can undertake towards a recrystallization process due to either heat or mechanical treatments. For instance, when sub-grain boundaries of the cells are enriched with Mo and higher concentration of dislocation, dynamical processes occur generating local residual stresses. In these circumstances the segregation of Mo in cell boundaries is out of thermodynamic equilibrium conditions so that microstructures and phases are metastable. In the range of 1100°-1400°C heat treatments a complete dissolution of Mo in the Fe matrix with a gradual disappearance of sub-microns cell is observed feeding the growth of larger austenitic sub-grains formation. It follows a higher degree of Mo dissolution in the material matrix and a decrease of dislocation's concentration [1]. In the work here presented we point out which are the microstructural features of stainless steel 316L components realized by Additive Manufacturing. Furthermore, the occurrence

of a microstructural evolution is presented after experiencing to fatigue of 80000 cycles some door joints obtained by this technique. A decrease of dislocation's number, an increase of twinning due to the growth of grains and to the release of local stresses can be hypothesized following that an important role could be played by the presence of dislocations in cell boundaries as well as oxides nano-inclusion formed in-situ during the Additive Manufacturing process [2]. From these outcomes it is going to be presented how the 3D components produced by Additive Manufacturing could change and improve their features for potential industrial applications during life cycles and enhance such a behavior by taking carefully into account the laser parameters and its scanning speed.

1. Introduction

Layer Manufacturing (LM) technologies like Selective Laser Sintering (SLS) were developed in the late 80's as an economic layer-by-layer near-net-shape for Rapid Prototyping (RP). Today its derived technology, that is Selective Laser Melting (SLM) or Additive Manufacturing (AM) is used as well for prototyping, tooling and manufacturing purposes. This process offers the undoubted advantage to process a large variety of materials with a broad range of physical and mechanical properties [3].

AM is a CAD/CAM technique that uses a layer-wise building principle, practically, a layer of powder is deposited in a bed and molten locally in a layer according to a computer aided design model [1]. The powder bed is then lowered and a new layer of loose powder is deposited, then the steps are repeated until the part is completed. In this way it is possible to fabricate metallic parts of complex geometries to avoid expensive tooling and post-machining and in particular it can give an important return to the market in terms of time consuming. Despite important advantages that AM process offers, it also faces with some problems, such as irregular porosity due to entrapped gas, structural deformation, balling, crack, lack of melting or poor wetting of a new layer on the material that was previously solidified [4-5]. All these implications cannot be easily avoided, inasmuch as AM process involves a large number of experimental variables, including laser power, laser beam wavelength, scanning speed and hatch distance of the laser beam incident onto the powder bed surface and material-based input parameters such as powder composition or its layer thickness. The interaction between these parameters has not been yet clearly understood, but it is possible to employ some strategies or controlling single parameters of the process in order to avoid some direct defects such as powder holder preheating, powder composition, laser power and its scan speed.

Another important feature of AM is that the structure undergoes an ultrafast cooling once the laser beam leaves the working zone, thus producing out-of-equilibrium microstructures. Furthermore the rapid heating of the powder due to the laser beam energy transfer process, which is followed by a rapid cooling rate, induces within the manufactured material a cellular structure with fine sub-grains belonging to the range of few hundred of micrometers. These metastable structures, which are smaller than the grain size observed in conventionally manufactured 316L stainless steel components, can undertake towards a re crystallization process due to heat treatments. For instance when sub-grain boundaries of the cells are enriched with Mo and higher concentration of dislocation, dynamical processes can occur generating local residual stresses. In these circumstances the segregation of Mo in cell boundaries is out of thermodynamic equilibrium conditions so that microstructures and phases are metastable. This study focuses on the microstructural features of some stainless steel components produced by AM. Specifically it is evidenced the role played by mechanical working cycle behaving like heat treatments in the range of 1100°-1400°C where a complete dissolution of Mo in the Fe matrix and a gradual disappearance of sub-microns cells is observed so that the growth of larger austenitic sub-grains formation can take place. It follows that a higher degree of Mo dissolution in the material matrix and a decrease of dislocation's concentration can be involved [1]. In particular the present study aims to verify a similar behavior where a microstructural evolution is caused after experiencing to fatigue of 80000 cycles some door joints stainless steel 316L produced by Additive Manufacturing.

2. Experimental approach

2.1 Investigated samples

The experimental activity has been focused on the characterization of different stainless steel 316L components produced by AM. These components are of two types: 1) for uses in automotive; 2) as components for pieces of furniture. For the former, a pump part has been produced by heating-up the powder bed support at 80°C (sample named FC) and by keeping it at room temperature (sample named FD). The latter regards door joints used for surgery storage supply cabinet where one has been investigated as it is after being produced (sample named 316L-AM-A) and the other after experiencing 80000 continuous working opening-closing cycles (sample named 316L-AM-B) both of them were manufactured by heating the power bed support at 80°C. The production parameters characteristics, such as laser parameters (scan speed, power etc.) and powder properties are not reported since the manufacturer does not want to reveal them. Nevertheless, these are not considered to be needed for highlighting the observed metastable character of the austenitic sub-

grains microstructural features detected for all samples here examined which, for the door joints, undergoes structural changes after 80000 working cycles.

2.2 Sample characterization

In order to characterize the composition, Brinell hardness, metallographic structural and microstructural features, and crystalline phases, the following different techniques have been used.

With the aim of distinguishing the properties of the longitudinal and transversal section of each sample these have been cut along the two directions by an abrasive cutter employing a cooling flow of water. For the metallographic preparation the specimens have been cold mounted in epoxy resins and after the use of SiC abrasive grinding papers ranging from very coarse 60 grit to very fine 1200 grit sizes and successively with abrasive diamond polishing and Al₂O₃ for final polishing (1mm).

The chemical analysis has been performed in five different parts of each sample in agreement with the UNI EN 573.3 (EN AW – 4046) test using an optical emission spectrometer for metal analysis (Bruker - Quantron Q8 Magellan). The Brinell hardness (HBW) has been addressed by inspecting six different parts of each sample in agreement with the UNI EN ISO 6506.1:2006 test by a Wolpert Dia Testor (force 187.5N, sphere diameter 2.5mm).

With the aim of inspecting the metallographic properties of all specimens in agreement with the UNI 3137:1965 test an electrolytic attack (1.1 V, HNO₃ 67%) has been applied and two different scale ranges of observation have been performed by employing both an Optical Microscope (Leica DM4 M) and Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM - Zeiss Supra-40 Field Emission) equipped with an Energy Dispersive Spectrometer microanalysis (Oxford X-Act 10x10 mm² Silicon Drift Detector). For addressing the crystalline properties of the samples diffractometric inspections have been provided by a Rigaku D-max Rapid micro-diffractometer (μ -XRD), operating at 40 kV and 30 mA which is equipped with a Cu-K α source, curved-image-plate detector, a flat graphite monochromator, a variety of beam collimators, a motorized stage and a microscope for accurate positioning of the sample. The motorized stage allows two angular movements (rotation Φ and revolution Ω). The data were collected in reflection mode using 0.3 mm collimator, a collection time of 20 min, a fixed Ω and Φ varying in the range $0^\circ \div 60^\circ$. The μ -XRD data were collected as two-dimensional images and then converted into 2θ -intensity profiles using the Rigaku R-Axis Display software.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Chemical Analysis

The following Table I and Table II show the chemical composition and the Brinell hardness data of the two types of specimens (FC, FD) and (316L-AM-A, 316L-AM-B) respectively.

As already mentioned two different sections of the samples were investigated, along the longitudinal and transversal plane of the components as reported for FC/FD and 316L-AM-A/B in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, respectively.

It can be highlighted that the two set of specimens, reported in Table I and Table II which are FC, FD and 316L-AM-A, 316L-AM-B respectively, show in general comparable Brinell hardness as well as compositional features of the surveyed samples.

3.2 Optical microscopy investigation - UNI 3137:1965

Both types of specimens at low magnification (4x) do not present any appreciable defects (cracks, voids etc.). For instance, some longitudinal and transversal sections of the FC and FD samples are hereafter reported (Fig. 3).

With regard to the door joints used for surgery storage supply cabinet as it is after being produced (316L-AM-A) and after experiencing 80000 continuous working opening-closing cycles (316L-AM-B) some longitudinal and transversal images acquired by optical microscopy with a magnification of 100x and 200x are reported in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, respectively. From these it can be observed that typical arcs induced by the incident laser spot are visible in the transversal section. These show microstructural features which are similar to those detected during the rapid cooling occurring in the arc shaped melt pool and the heat-affected-zone induced by laser welding. In a similar way all additive manufactured samples here investigated present such a character which, at larger magnifications, displays dendritic, acicular, cellular etc. microstructural features (e.g. Fig. 4 transversal section, 200x).

Fig. 5 shows that after 80000 working cycles the door joints used for surgery storage supply cabinet display a well visible change of the microstructural feature in both the transverse and longitudinal sections here investigated. Moreover, there is the presence of circular defects homogeneously distributed and extended grains, that means in the range of 300-400 μm , which are characterised by a typical austenitic structure.

3.3 μ -XRD diffractometric inspection

The diffractometric data have evidenced that the crystalline phase present in all sample under study could just be related to the austenitic γ phase. As a matter of example Fig.6 shows the typical austenitic γ phase crystallographic peaks of the fcc planes (111), (200), (220) and (331) at 2θ values

of 43.56, 50.73, 74.71 and 90.60, respectively detected for the longitudinal section of both FC and FD samples.

3.5 Scanning electron microscopy and microanalysis

3.5.1 FC and FD specimens

For both sections of the FC and FD samples similar microstructures already detected by optical microscopy have been observed. Fig.7 shows the occurrence of an apparent variety of stainless steel microstructures (e.g. pearlite, bainite, martensite etc.). Nevertheless, considering the μ -XRD data it can be hypothesized that just a metastable austenitic phase is present as a consequence of the rapid cooling process experienced by the melted powder. Fig.7 shows the typical microstructure observed for all samples which for simplicity it is referred to the investigated sections of the specimen FD. The austenitic grain shape is well recognizable in the bottom right corner of both investigated sections of the FD images. In order to highlight if any change in composition could be involved in the different microstructural domains punctual EDS microanalyses of the samples have been performed. In Fig. 8 the microanalysis of the transversal section of the FD specimen reported in Fig. 7 is shown. A part of some deviation in spectrum 1, 2 and 6 the wt% of the major components is comparable for all investigated microstructural domains.

These data can further confirm that the very fast cooling process experienced by the powder after the laser melting induces the occurrence of apparent different microstructural phases, which, however, should be related to different forms of the austenitic γ one. The temperature gradients involved during the rapid cooling process can play a key role in the observed phenomenon as well as causing a limited growth of the typical austenitic grains which, as shown in Fig. 9, display dimensions of just few hundred of nanometers.

The microstructural observations performed by SEM on the two sections of the FC and FD specimens have shown that the heating of the powder bed support can play a role in the formation of spherical discontinuities into the produced component. As it is shown in Fig.10, the longitudinal section of the FD specimen displays the presence of balling which formation, on the contrary of the sample FC, where it has not been detected, could be favoured from the lack of heating-up the powder bed support. It follows that the temperature gradient can play two roles: 1) inducing the presence of metastable microstructural different forms of the same phase (in this work the austenitic γ one); 2) producing defects such as balling which can be caused by capillary motions present within the laser melted pool due to local surface tension gradients (e.g. Marangoni flow). While the latter can be

controlled by a proper choice of the laser parameters used (e.g. scan speed, energy etc.) or, as it has been revealed from our data by heating-up the power bed support, the occurrence of a metastable phase is unavoidable.

With the purpose of following the microstructural evolution of the observed different morphologies of the metastable γ phase we have focussed our attention on the effects played on the door joints undergoing to 80000 working cycles. In Fig. 11 the SEM image of 316L-AM-A longitudinal section is reported together with microanalysis of some different microstructural zones of it.

The typical acicular, dendritic etc. microstructural features already observed for the FC and FD specimens are still present and their composition confirms that the same phase is representative for all different zones investigated. Even in this case the μ -XRD data let us consider that the bcc austenitic γ is the only phase characterizing the 316L-AM-A sample. After 80000 working cycles, however, this scenario changes on both microstructural and compositional aspects. Fig. 12 reports the observed variations.

It is evident that strong changes are involved which are related to: 1) the microstructure, already observed by optical microscopy, where the grains have become larger than ten of micrometers; 2) compositional loss of Ni and Mo which can be in the range of 30%-100%.

Discussion

The diffractometric data as well as the compositional ones support the hypothesis that all samples as they are produced present only the γ austenitic phase. The Schaeffler diagram undergoes an expansion or constriction of the gamma sector by means of alloying elements such as Ni, Mn etc. or Cr, Mo etc., respectively. This means that in the latter case austenitic to ferrite (γ - α) transformation can be maintained down to ambient temperature. Looking at the door joint compositional features after 80000 working cycles it can be supposed that, especially along the grain boundaries and depicted spherical defects, the amount of chromium can be much higher than the nickel equivalent one so that phase transformations can occur. As it has been observed in the previous sections, the high temperature gradients taking place during the laser melting and successive cooling down of the powders can strongly characterize the microstructural features of the whole additive manufacturing process. The temperature gradients taking place are modeled mathematically and can well support the occurrence of a fast cooling down process which can lead to formation of metastable structures [6, 7]. If the Continuous Cooling Transformation (CCT) curves and the thermal properties of additive manufacturing process are taken into account it can be expected that different microstructures of the same austenitic phase are formed during the treatment of 316L stainless steel

powders. In this circumstances one can consider the additive manufacturing of metals to be similar to micro-welding processes where, due to the strong thermal gradients induced into the welding-pool, acicular, dendritic etc. microstructures take place [8]. Moreover, the austenitic nanograins of few hundreds of nanometers as well as the other microstructures observed demonstrate that the temperature gradient G and the speed of growth R play a crucial role in determining the morphology and dimensions of the microstructural domains here observed [9].

From the peculiarities of the additive manufacturing process here reported it is not surprising to consider the 316L specimens under investigation to be formed by continuous microwelded metastable parts. Nevertheless, it could not be envisaged that after 80000 working cycles the door joints could show evident microstructural changes. The formation of large austenitic grains could take place as a transformation of the different microstructural metastable γ phase domains of the specimen as a consequence of local heating caused by the working cycles. The compositional variations detected could be caused by the dissolution of intermetallic phases, which could be occurred during the metallographic preparation of the sample, localized at either the grain boundaries or the spherical defects. In a recent work [1] it is reported that a similar behaviour could be due to recrystallization and growth of the microstructures together with migration towards the grain boundaries of some elements such as Mo and successive precipitation of intermetallic phases. In particular it is hypothesized that microcrystalline structures obtained by additive manufacturing have a high degree of dislocations and Mo enrichment at the grain boundaries of the single substructures.

Such behaviours, which are essentially due to dynamic processes, induce local residual stresses and segregation of metallic species (e.g. Mo) which do not fulfil the thermodynamic equilibrium conditions. Taking into account that 316L stainless steel components obtained by additive manufacturing can increase their hardness after thermal treatments [2] it follows that different processes not involving the austenite-martensite transformation should take place. With this regard one possible route considers the presence of both dislocations at the unit cell boundaries and oxides nanoinclusions formed *in-situ*. Consequently, after long annealing the 316L stainless steel obtained by additive manufacturing could induce: removal of the residual stresses; recrystallization or growth of the crystalline phases as well as phase transformations. Recrystallization are complex processes thermally activated in saturation sites which develop, overcoming the grains previously formed, by nucleation and growth of new crystals free of stresses. Moreover, after annealing in the range of 1100-1400 °C it has been observed: 1) a decrease of dislocations; 2) the disappearance of the different microstructural acicular, dendritic etc. domains and the formation of large austenitic

grains. These effects, which are well visible for an annealing at 1400°C cause the formation of twinings. Furthermore, the 316L stainless steel components produced by additive manufacturing could in any case be characterized by a undetectable amount of ferrite which, after thermal treatment, could be stabilized by Mo. As a matter of facts, at low temperatures the Mo, which has an atomic radius (1.94 Å) larger than Fe (1.56 Å) could not have the right mobility for getting incorporated within the ferrite matrix which, on the contrary, can happen at the austenitic grain boundaries at high temperatures. Fig. 12 has shown that a such mechanism could be involved even in the 316L-AM-B specimen after 80000 working cycles, maybe, because of a combination of mechanical and thermal effects which could reproduce the results of a high temperature annealing.

Conclusions

The data here presented about laser Additive Manufactured 316L stainless steel components show for all the samples investigated that a micro-welding like process is involved. This provides a strict relationship between the micro-structural properties of the samples and the typical thermal history of the additive manufacturing process. Heating the power bed support the formation of defects can be avoided although all the other working parameters (i.e. laser power, scan speed etc.) can noticeably affect the properties of the final component which in any case is characterized by metastable microstructures. These microstructures represent different morphologies of the same austenitic γ phase. After experiencing a door joint to 80000 working cycles the metastable microstructures undergo to transformation into larger grains and migration of some elements such as Mo towards the grain boundaries and spherical defects. This process could induce the formation of ferritic phases, a decrease of the number of dislocations and the development within the component of twinings which reflect well the changes induced on additive manufactured components after high temperature annealing [1].

Acknowledgements

This paper draws on work undertaken as part of the project agreement “Characterization and comparison of stainless steel 304 and 316 L components manufactured by conventional and Additive Manufacturing techniques” between the Scientific Research Area of Trieste (Basilicata Innovation Project, ITALY) and the Institute of the Structure of Matter (CNR-ITALY). The authors would like to express their gratefulness to Engr. Dr. Renzo Sarli Calace and Mr. Paolo Mander who involved them on this fascinating subject.

References

- [1] K. Saeidi, X. Gao, F. Lofaj, L. Kvetková, Z.J. Shen, Transformation of austenite to duplex austenite-ferrite assembly in annealed stainless steel 316L consolidated by laser melting, *J. Alloys Comp.*, **633** (2015), 463-469
- [2] K. Saeidi, X. Gao, Y. Zhong, Z.J. Shen, Hardened austenite steel with columnar sub-grain structure formed by laser melting, *Mater. Sci. Eng. A* **625** (2015), 221-229
- [3] J.P. Kruth, P. Mercelis, J. Van Vaerenbergh, L. Froyen, M. Rombouts, Binding Mechanisms in Selective Laser Sintering and Selective Laser Melting, *Rapid Prototyping J.*, **55** (1) (2005), 26–36
- [4] A. Mertens, S. Reginster, H. Paydas, Q. Contrepois, T. Dormal, O. Lemaire, J. Lecomte-Beckers, Mechanical properties of alloy Ti-6Al-4V and of stainless 316L processed by selective laser melting: influence of out-of-equilibrium microstructures, *Powder Metall.*, **7** (2014), 184-188
- [5] B. Zhang, L. Dembinski, C. Coddet, The study of the laser parameters and environments variables effect on mechanical properties of high compact parts elaborated by selective laser melting 316L powder, *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, **584** (2013), 21-31
- [6] S.A. Khairallah and A. Anderson, Mesoscopic simulation model of selective laser melting of stainless steel powder, *J. Mater. Process. Technol.*, **214** (2014), 2627–2636
- [7] A. Hussein, L. Hao, C. Yan and R. Everson, Finite element simulation of the temperature and stress fields in single layers built without-support in selective laser melting, *Materials and Design*, **52** (2013) pp.638–647
- [8] S.A. David and T. Debroy, Current issues and problems in welding science, *Science* **257** (1992) 497-502
- [9] *Welding Metallurgy*, 2nd Ed., Sindo Kou, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken, New Jersey, 2003, p.166

Figures captions

Fig.1 Sections investigated for the FC and FD samples. Longitudinal and transversal plane of the components are referred to position 1 and position 2, respectively.

Fig.2 Sections investigated for the 316L-AM-A and 316L-AM-B samples. Longitudinal and transversal plane of the components are referred to 2L and 1T, respectively.

Fig.3 Longitudinal and transversal sections of the FC and FD specimens observed by optical microscopy at low magnification (4x).

Fig.4 Longitudinal and transversal sections of the stainless steel 316L-AM-A specimen observed by optical microscopy at a magnification of 100x and 200x.

Fig.5 Longitudinal and transversal sections of the stainless steel 316L-AM-B specimen observed by optical microscopy at a magnification of 100x and 200x.

Fig.6 Typical μ -XRD spectra of the position 1 section of the FC and FD specimens.

Fig.7 Microstructure of the FD stainless steel 316L component.

Fig.8 Microanalysis of the transversal section of the FD specimen reported in Fig. 7.

Fig.9 Image of typical austenitic nanograins. Transverse section of the specimen FD.

Fig.10 Distinctive balling effect observed in the longitudinal section of the specimen FD.

Fig.11 Microanalysis of different zones of the longitudinal section of the 316L-AM-A specimen.

Fig.12 Microanalysis of different zones of the longitudinal section of the 316L-AM-B specimen.

Table I

FC-FD Brinell hardness and chemical analysis investigation. Other element contents not reported are: P=0.007 wt%, S=0.002 wt%, P=0.018 wt% and S=0.001wt%, respectively; Fe balance.

<i>Sample</i>	Hardness HBW10	<i>C wt%</i> ±0.005	<i>Si wt%</i> ±0.001	<i>Mn wt%</i> ±0.001	<i>N wt%</i> ±0.001	<i>Cr wt%</i> ±0.01	<i>Ni wt%</i> ±0.01	<i>Mo wt%</i> ±0.001
FC	205±4	0.010	0.400	1.411	0.026	17.69	16.14	2.591
Ref	---	0.03 max	0.75 max	2.0 max	0.10 max	16.0÷18.0	10.0÷14.0	2.0÷3.0
FD	212±4	0.010	0.625	1.436	0.050	17.55	14.32	2.206

Table II

316L-AM-A and 316L-AM-B Brinell hardness and chemical analysis investigation. Other element contents not reported are: P=0.045 wt%, S=0.03 wt%, P=0.017 wt% and S=0.008wt%, respectively; Fe balance.

<i>Sample</i>	Hardness <i>HBW10</i>	<i>C wt%</i> ± 0.005	<i>Si wt%</i> ± 0.001	<i>Mn wt%</i> ± 0.001	<i>N wt%</i> ± 0.001	<i>Cr wt%</i> ± 0.01	<i>Ni wt%</i> ± 0.01	<i>Mo wt%</i> ± 0.001
AM-A	229±2	0.014	0.608	1.341	0.050	18.40	12.38	2.115
Ref.	---	0.03 max	0.75 max	2.0 max	0.10 max	16.0÷18.0	10.0÷14.0	2.0÷3.0
AM-B	201.5±6.5	0.013	0.627	1.352	0.051	18.36	12.47	2.091

Figure1
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Cutting directions

Figure2
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure3
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure4
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure5
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure6
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure7
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Position 1

Position 2

Figure8
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

<i>Element (wt%)</i>	<i>Fe</i>	<i>Si</i>	<i>Mn</i>	<i>Cr</i>	<i>Ni</i>
<i>Spectrum</i>					
1	61.7	---	2.0	18.8	15.1
2	63.6	---	---	19.0	14.8
3	61.3	2.5	1.6	17.1	15.3
4	61.7	1.0	1.9	18.2	14.0
5	60.8	2.0	2.3	17.7	13.2
6	62.4	---	2.0	18.2	15.0

Figure9
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure10
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 11
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

<i>Element</i>	<i>Wt%</i>
Si	0.77
Cr	18.19
Mn	1.59
Fe	64.10
Ni	12.75
Mo	2.61

Figure12
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

<i>Element (wt%)</i> <i>Spectrum</i>	<i>Si</i>	<i>Cr</i>	<i>Mn</i>	<i>Fe</i>	<i>Ni</i>	<i>Mo</i>
Matrix	0.39	20.48	3.07	66.28	7.81	1.97
Dot	0.45	19.24	2.22	69.61	7.98	0.49
Grain boundary	0.36	19.29	2.53	69.20	8.17	0.45
Grain boundary	0.40	19.59	2.51	69.65	7.85	0.00
Dot	0.33	19.77	2.35	69.74	7.81	0.00